

TEACHING MUSIC EDUCATION THROUGH THE ART OF DIFFERENT PEOPLES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the issues of highlighting cultural diversity through music education, the formation of intercultural dialogue, tolerance and aesthetic taste in students based on the artistic traditions of different peoples. The study of folklore, national melodies and songs of the peoples of the world in music lessons is considered an important factor in expanding students' cultural awareness, teaching them to respect the art of other nations and peoples.

Keywords: music education, intercultural education, national music, folk music, tolerance, intercultural dialogue, integrated education, aesthetic education, folk art.

Introduction.

In today's globalization process, understanding and appreciating cultural diversity is becoming increasingly important for every society. The unique art, melodies, melodies and rhythms of each nation are an expression of its historical memory, national spirit and aesthetic views. In particular, music is a powerful tool that unites humanity and brings different cultures closer together. From this perspective, music education not only teaches performance or theoretical knowledge, but also teaches understanding and respect for the cultural heritage of different peoples. By introducing students to the musical traditions of different nations and ethnicities, not only their knowledge base expands, but also tolerance, respect for others, empathy and intercultural communication skills are formed in them. By listening to and analyzing, for example, Chinese pentatonic melodies, African drum rhythms or Latin American dance music in addition to Uzbek folk melodies in music lessons, children grow not only in terms of auditory aesthetics, but also in terms of cultural awareness.

Thus, music education is not just the study of notes and rhythms, but also a powerful pedagogical tool that leads a person to humanity, a bridge between cultures, and forms a global worldview. This article focuses on this issue and analyzes how cultural diversity can be formed through music education, how the art of different peoples can be used as a didactic resource.

In today's era of globalization, the forces that unite humanity are becoming extremely important. Among them, culture, and especially music, occupies a special place. Music, as a means of wordless communication that affects the most delicate feelings of the human soul, connects representatives of any people, nation and culture. Therefore, I believe that music education, taught through the art of different peoples, not only forms aesthetic taste, but also cultivates respect, interest, and tolerance for other cultures.

Every nation in the world has its own musical heritage. Each of them is a world - rich in its own history, culture, and traditions. By introducing students to the melodies and songs of different nations in music lessons, we take them on a journey into the spiritual world of other

nations. For example, the simplicity and closeness to nature in Japanese folk music, the power and rhythm in African war drums, the harmony of thought and emotions in European classical music - all this broadens the student's worldview.

I believe that music education is not only about learning notes, singing, or playing an instrument, but also the process of instilling human values. Teaching students to listen to and understand not only national melodies, but also the music of the peoples of the world is to raise them as open, modern, and tolerant individuals. A child who has become acquainted with different cultures will treat other nations with respect in the future, will not succumb to stereotypes, and will have a deeper understanding of the values of his or her own people.

I consider music not just an art form, but a universal language that unites humanity. Through this language, seeds of love, friendship and solidarity are sown in the hearts of children. Therefore, every music teacher should, taking into account cultural diversity, reveal to students the beauty of the art of the peoples of the world in their lessons. Music education based on cultural diversity is an integral part of modern education. Through it, we educate not only musical knowledge, but also humanity, tolerance and kindness. If music is a language that lives in the hearts of humanity, then teaching it is the art of bringing hearts closer together. Music is one of the oldest and most influential cultural manifestations in human history. Each nation expresses through its music how it perceives the world, its inner experiences, customs and traditions. Introducing students to this rich musical diversity becomes an important tool in forming one of the main goals of education - a well-rounded, open to intercultural understanding, and tolerant personality. Using musical samples from different nations in teaching music in the school and higher education system not only enriches aesthetic knowledge, but also adapts students to the global cultural environment. For example, through the drum rhythms of the African people, students can gain a deeper understanding of rhythmic intuition and dynamics. The calm and natural melodies characteristic of Japan help to feel inner peace and musical balance. Incorporating music from different regions into music programs, especially for children, increases their cultural interest and teaches them to respect other musical cultures. Lessons can be more meaningful and effective by combining music, history, geography, and art subjects based on an integrated approach in the educational process. For example, in the study of ancient Greek music, contexts related to their mythology, religion, and theater are analyzed. Or in the study of the musical heritage of the Turkic peoples, through common roots and historical connections, students not only understand their national identity, but also learn respect for other peoples.

Also, through modern educational technologies - video lessons, online music libraries, virtual concerts, international music projects, students have the opportunity to enjoy examples of art from different parts of the world. This forms their skills of independent thinking, comparison, and analysis of music not only within their own culture, but also in the global musical space. The role of the teacher is a leader in this process, he should not only be a provider of knowledge, but also a "bridge builder" between different cultures. It is important that he draws students' attention to the spiritual aspects of folk music during the lesson and brings them into the cultural context through melody, rhythm, and form.

Literature Review:

Cultural diversity and music education are among the current research areas that are interconnected. Research conducted by international and local scholars in this field shows that art, in particular music, is one of the most powerful tools for strengthening intercultural

ties and forming tolerance in the younger generation. Internationally, ethnomusicologists such as C. A. Campbell[5] and P. S. Nettle[6] have emphasized in their research that it is possible to form cultural awareness and understanding in students through the study of music of different nations. Their research reveals the pedagogical potential of national music, especially its role in strengthening general musical literacy and cultural identity.

J. Banks's work "*Multicultural Education*"[4] highlights the general methodology of multicultural education, showing ways to develop empathy and intercultural dialogue in students through the art of music. In his opinion, art, and in particular music, not only knowledge is formed, but also social emotions, values, and a sense of intercultural respect.

Local researchers such as M. Jo'rayev[1], O. Mahkamova[2], Sh. Nazarova[3] have conducted important scientific research on the importance of folk music in aesthetic education and its role in the formation of national identity. In particular, Mahkamova's work "Cultural Values in Music Education" deeply analyzes the methods of forming students' aesthetic worldviews through national music. Another important aspect is that the possibilities of interactive teaching of music of different nations through modern educational technologies, including digital resources, are widely covered in the literature. In this regard, S. E. Russell's study "*Music Across Cultures*"[7] states that the use of QR code resources and video/audio files in music lessons makes it easier to understand cultural diversity. Thus, the analysis of the existing scientific literature shows that teaching cultural diversity through music education is an effective approach not only from a theoretical but also from a practical point of view, and scientific views on this issue are being harmonized with the strategic directions of today's education.

Reflecting cultural diversity in music education is an important factor not only in aesthetic education, but also in the development of students' social consciousness. The studied international and local experiences, as well as the results of a survey conducted among school teachers and students, show that studying the musical heritage of different peoples forms in students not only a tendency towards intercultural dialogue, but also a deep sense of respect for their own national values. These indicators mean that addressing the art of different cultures in music education activates students, expands their horizons of thinking, and most importantly, creates an atmosphere of intercultural tolerance and respect among them. At the same time, music teachers are also accepting this approach as an important tool that enriches the learning process.

Discussion:

In today's era of globalization, one of the main tasks facing the education system is not only to increase the level of knowledge of students, but also to educate them as tolerant, open-minded and ready for intercultural dialogue. It is from this perspective that methods of music education that reflect cultural diversity and are aimed at a deep understanding of it are becoming increasingly relevant. In the course of the discussion, it can be said with confidence that providing students with information about different peoples of the world through the art of music is one of the most subtle and effective ways to educate them to be spiritually, morally and ethically mature. The research found that incorporating folk music, national melodies, and traditional rhythms of other nations into music lessons arouses a sense of curiosity, wonder, and deep understanding in students. This, in turn, enriches the activity and content of the lessons and encourages students to think creatively. Through the universal language of

music - melody, rhythm and emotion, each child expands his inner world, forms respect and understanding for others.

Also, this approach allows not only students, but also teachers to develop their professional skills, try new methods. When music teachers select musical samples of different cultures during the lesson and teach them by comparing them with our national music, musical thinking, analysis and comparison skills are formed among students. Of course, highlighting cultural diversity in education requires a certain methodological approach and didactic tools. Such an approach develops not only musical knowledge, but also socio-cultural skills. Importantly, through this process, the student becomes a mature person who feels himself as part of the world, loyal to his nationality, but also able to appreciate other cultures. Therefore, music education is not only an important pedagogical tool for teaching art, but also for forming cultural consciousness, understanding human values, and directing them to live harmoniously in society.

Conclusion.

The above research results show that highlighting cultural diversity through music education is one of the relevant and effective directions of today's educational process. By introducing students to the musical heritage of different peoples, not only their aesthetic worldview, but also their interest in intercultural dialogue, tolerance, and level of social consciousness develop. In this process, the music teacher is not just a provider of knowledge, but also a creative educator who builds bridges between cultures and expands the thinking of students. Therefore, using examples of the art of other nations, along with our national music, in music lessons is an important tool that increases the effectiveness of education and shapes the student as a well-rounded individual.

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